

CLINICAL-DIAGNOSTIC AND PROGNOSTIC FEATURES OF DETERMINING THE LEVEL OF OXYPROLINE IN THE BLOOD IN CHILDREN WITH ACUTE OBSTRUCTIVE BRONCHITIS

Zafarova M.Z.

Student 227 gr., faculty of pediatry. Samarkand medical university.

Mukhsinova M. Kh.

Scientific supervisor:

Associate Professor of the Department of Therapeutic Subjects No. 1

Utepova G.B.

Associate Professor of the Department of Therapeutic Subjects No. 1

Tashkent State Dental Institute, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10617383>

In recent years, shifts in immune reactivity have been given a certain place in the dysregulation of collagen synthesis during inflammatory processes in the lungs. A number of researchers associate the intensity of collagen formation in acute inflammatory diseases in the lungs with metabolic disorders associated with proteins, in particular hydroxyproline. To date, metabolic disorders of the connective tissue structures of the lungs and collagen degradation in obstructive bronchitis have not been sufficiently studied.

The purpose of the study was to study the clinical significance of hydroxyproline shifts for assessing the severity and outcome of the disease, developing adequate methods for correcting hydroxyproline metabolism in the treatment of young children with acute obstructive bronchitis.

Material and methods of research: we examined 95 children aged from 1 month to 3 years (average age 1.5 ± 0.63 years). The first group included patients with acute obstructive bronchitis, in whom the level of hydroxyproline was studied before and after treatment, from 53 of them received traditional treatment and in the second 40, along with traditional treatment, they received Immunomodulin. The control group consisted of 20 practically healthy - children of the same age. The duration of treatment was on average 8-12 days. Immunomodulin was prescribed intramuscularly in a 0.1-0.014% solution per 10 kg of body weight once a week for 5-7 days.

Results and discussion. Analysis of our research results showed that before treatment, the level of free and protein-bound hydroxyproline in the blood plasma of young children with acute obstructive bronchitis was significantly higher than in the control group.

Changes in hydroxyproline metabolism indicate the heterogeneity of pathomorphological disorders in the bronchopulmonary system, which is accompanied by a different course and severity of the clinical picture of the

disease. At the same time, significant changes in collagen metabolism found in our studies in the body of young children with acute obstructive bronchitis indicate the need for correction of the identified disorders .

As the results of our studies have shown, the level of free and protein- bound hydroxyproline is restored to the control value when Immunomodulin is included in the traditional treatment regimen.

Along with the improvement in hydroxyproline metabolism, we noted that the administration of Immunomodulin contributes to an earlier improvement in the clinical manifestations of the disease and a reduction in the recovery period. Thus, after 1-2 injections of the drug in children, the body temperature decreased to normal, the average duration of the febrile period remained 1.8 ± 0.1 days, whereas in children with traditional treatment, the duration of body temperature above 37.5°C ($38-39^{\circ} \text{C}$) persisted for 2-3 days and averaged 2.5 ± 0.2 days ($p < 0.001$).

Thus, the identified difference in the content of hydroxyproline in the blood plasma in patients with acute obstructive bronchitis indicates its diagnostic and prognostic significance for assessing the severity, nature of the course and outcome of the disease, as well as for analyzing the effectiveness of therapy. The higher therapeutic effect of Immunomodulin compared to the traditional method of treatment, revealed in our studies , allows us to recommend it for the treatment of young children with acute obstructive bronchitis, which will help optimize therapy.

Literary references:

1. Nazarenko I.M., Kuzmenko L.G., Petruk N.I. Features of phagocytosis, immune and interferon status in young children with recurrent obstructive bronchitis // Pediatrics. – M., 2011. - No. 5. – pp. 21-23
2. Mukhsinova M. Kh., Ubaidullaeva O. Kh., Aripova G. M., Atashikova R. M. Features of the course of acute obstructive bronchitis and bronchiolitis in young children when corrected with immunomodulin. //Re-health journal. 1(9) 2021. pp. 110-116.
3. Mukhsinova M., Yunusova R., Ilkhamova Kh. Assessment of the severity of acute obstructive bronchitis and bronchiolitis in early children depending on the level of oxiprolin in the blood. // Uzbek medical journal. No. 1. 2021. P.5-11.
4. Mukhsinova M. Kh., Ubaydullaeva O.H. Diagnostic and therapeutic aspects of acute exercise bronchitis in children. // Uzbek medical journal. No. 6. 2021. P. 51-56.

5. Teixeira M.F.C, Rodrigues J.C. et al. || Acute bronchodilator responsiveness to tiotropium in postinfectious bronchiolitis obliterans in children.|| Chest. 2013 Sep;144(3):974-980. doi: 10.1378/chest.12-2280.
6. Usenko S.H., Yeloeva Z.V. et al. || Clinical and laboratory aspects of acute obstructive bronchitis in children infected with mycoplasma pneumonia||Wiad Lek. 2020;73(6):1229-1233.
7. Xing Y., Proesmans M.|| New therapies for acute RSV infections: where are we?||Eur J Pediatr. 2019 Feb;178(2):131-138. doi: 10.1007/s00431-018-03310-7. Epub 2019 Jan 4.

